

Egg Quality Traits of French Pekin Ducks Reared Under the Indoor Housing Systems

Nasir Abdallah*^{ID}, Kadriye Kursun^{ID}, Mikail Baylan^{ID}
Çukurova University, Department of Animal Science, Adana, Türkiye
*Corresponding author: nasirmayam@gmail.com

Abstract

A total of 17 eggs of French Pekin ducks reared indoors under standard environmental conditions (20-22°C and 55-60% RH) on a private duck breeding farm were used in the current study. The eggs were assessed for their internal and external egg quality traits using the destructive method. The average egg weight, egg width and egg height were 90.25±1.51g, 48.26±0.29 mm, and 69.10±0.68 mm respectively. The egg breaking strength or resistance, shape index, eggshell thickness and shell weight were 2.99±0.39 kg/cm², 69.93±0.72%, 414.76±5.99 mm and 8.28±0.15 g respectively. The shell percentage and elongation values were 9.19±0.15% and 1.43±0.01 respectively.

The average yolk height, yolk width and yolk weight were 21.35±0.23 mm, 50.79±0.53 mm and 35.02±0.98 g respectively. The L (brightness), a (redness) and b (yellowness) yolk color traits were 55.67±0.46, 13.06±0.37 and 55.60±0.88 respectively. The yolk index and yolk percentage were 42.07±0.49% and 38.85±0.96% respectively.

The albumen height, albumen width and albumen length were 8.16±0.23 mm, 67.91±1.21 mm and 106.26±1.63 mm respectively. The albumen pH, albumen weight and albumen index were 9.30±0.11, 42.01±0.88g and 9.39±0.30% respectively. The albumen percentage and yolk to albumen ratio were 46.67±1.02% and 84.03±3.14% respectively. The Haugh unit was 82.43±1.51%.

It was concluded the internal and external egg quality traits of the French Pekin ducks observed in this study were within the normal range.

Keywords: Egg quality, Pekin ducks, performance

Introduction

The rise in the global consumption of chicken egg especially, in third world countries has increased the global demand for chicken egg production. This has also led to the production and consumption of eggs from other poultry species to meet the global demand for chicken eggs. One of the poultry species with low production and maintenance cost but high egg and meat nutritive value is Pekin ducks. Compared to chicken eggs, duck eggs have been reported to have higher protein, energy, carbohydrate, vitamins, iron, and sodium content [1]. Other authors have also reported duck eggs as a good source of protein and other nutrients, and are regarded as a food with high nutritional quality [2,3].

Moreover, duck eggs have high nutritional value due to its essential amino acids and fatty acids composition coupled with a high percentage of polyunsaturated fatty acids and a favorable ratio of omega 6- to omega 3-fatty acids [2]. Furthermore, the albumen of ducks contains about 60% methionine, by 30% threonine, by 25% tryptophan and by 45% sulfur amino acids higher than that of hen eggs [4]. It is also estimated that duck egg consumption accounts for 10–30% of total egg consumption in China and Southeast Asia [5]. In China, 80% of the total egg production is from chickens, and the remaining are primarily from ducks and quails [6]. China is also the largest producer of duck eggs in the Asian continent [7]. It was also reported that in 2015 in Thailand, a total of 13,548,366 ducks were used to produce eggs, of which free-grazing duck farms located mainly in the western and central areas of Thailand constituted about 51.86% [8].

The internal and external egg quality traits are important since it influences the purchasing power of the consumer and the total economic gains of the farmer. For instance, consumers have developed a unique desirability for a certain yolk color, egg weight and shell thickness which has to meet by farmers. Egg breaking strength and shell thickness are important economic parameters and in chicken egg production, egg breakage has been reported serve as a medium of egg contamination and constitute about 8-11% of the total egg loss [9]. An estimated value of 7.77% egg loss in poultry units due to poor shell

quality are estimated have been reported by [10]. Further losses due to egg breakage during egg collection and handling by consumer has been reported to be around 6.37% [11] and the total of the losses, which is around 14.14%, translated into more than \$47 million economic loss when applied to production figures for 1992 [12]. Due to these reasons, the quality of an egg is an important economic parameter to consider for both small scale and large-scale egg producers.

Therefore, this work aimed at evaluating the internal and external egg quality traits of French Pekin ducks reared in litter production system.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at the Laboratory of Çukurova University using a total of 17 eggs of French Pekin ducks at 60 week of age obtained from a commercial private farm. The eggs were assessed for internal and external egg quality traits using the destructive methods.

Measurement of Internal and External Egg Quality Traits

The width and height of the eggs were measured using an electronic Vernier calliper. The Shape index was evaluated by dividing the egg width by the height of the egg and multiplying it by 100 percent. The shell and egg weight were recorded using an electronic scale with 0.01g precision.

The eggs were then cracked on a transparent square glass and the dimensions (Height and width and length) of yolk and albumen were recorded using a vernier caliper. the albumen index and yolk index were evaluated using the measured albumen and yolk dimensions in mathematical formulae. The albumen and yolk were collected in a separate petri dish and weighed using an electronic balance. The albumen was then transferred into a disposable cup and pH meter was inserted in it for the measurement of the pH value. The yolk was collected into a petri dish and then placed into a Konica Minolta Colorimeter CR-300 device to determine the yolk colour values (L: brightness, a: redness, and b: yellowness).

For the measurement of the shell thickness, the portion of each part of the shell (narrow, middle, and broad parts) was recorded with a shell thickness gauge and the average of the 3 parts was recorded.

The egg-breaking strength was conducted by placing the egg on an egg-breaking device, TA-XT Plus Brand Texture Analyzer. The egg was held until the device made physical contact with the egg. The experimenter then removed their hand from the egg while the device exerted mild pressure on the egg. Once the egg was broken, the force at which the egg was broken was automatically recorded on a laptop screen connected to the egg-breaking device.

The formula below was used in evaluating the respective traits.

$$\text{Shell thickness} = \frac{(\text{Broad. Narrow and Middle parts})}{3}$$

$$\text{Shape Index} = \frac{\text{Egg Width (mm)}}{\text{Egg Length (mm)}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Albumen Index} = \frac{\text{Albumen height (mm)}}{\text{Average of Albumen Width and Length (mm)}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Yolk Index} = \frac{\text{Yolk height (mm)}}{\text{Yolk Width (mm)}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Haugh unit} = 100 \log (\text{Albumen Height} + 7.57 - 1.7 \times \text{Egg Weight}^{0.37})$$

$$\text{Albumen percentage} = \frac{\text{Albumen Weight}}{\text{Egg Weight}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Yolk percentage} = \frac{\text{Yolk Weight}}{\text{Egg Weight}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Shell Percentage} = \frac{\text{Shell Weight}}{\text{Egg Weight}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Yolk; Albumen Ratio} = \frac{\text{Yolk Weight}}{\text{Albumen Weight}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Elongation} = \frac{\text{Egg Height}}{\text{Egg Width}}$$

Results and Discussion

Table 1. The external egg quality traits of French Pekin ducks

Egg weight (g)	90.25 ± 1.51
Egg length (mm)	69.10 ± 0.68
Egg width (mm)	48.26 ± 0.29
Egg breaking strength (kg/cm ²)	2.99 ± 0.39
Shape index (%)	69.93 ± 0.72
Eggshell thickness (mm)	414.76 ± 5.99
Shell weight with membranes (g)	8.28 ± 0.15
Shell percentage (%)	9.19 ± 0.15
Elongation	1.43 ± 0.01

The average egg weight, egg width and egg length were 90.25±1.51 g, 48.26±0.29 mm, and 69.10±0.68 mm respectively. The egg breaking strength or resistance, shape index, eggshell thickness and shell weight were 2.99±0.39 kg/cm², 69.93±0.72%, 414.76±5.99 mm and 8.28±0.15 g respectively. The shell percentage and elongation values were 9.19±0.15% and 1.43±0.01 respectively. Similar to the findings in the current study, other authors [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18] have reported similar egg weight, shell thickness, egg height, egg width, elongation, shell weight, shell breaking strength and shape index values in French Pekin ducks or Pekin ducks of other natives.

Table 2. The yolk quality traits of French Pekin ducks evaluated

Yolk weight (g)	35.02 ± 0.98
Yolk length (mm)	21.35 ± 0.23
Yolk width (mm)	50.79 ± 0.53
Yolk index (%)	42.07 ± 0.49
Yolk percentage (%)	38.85 ± 0.96
Yolk Color Traits	
L* (brightness)	55.67 ± 0.46
a* (redness)	13.06 ± 0.37
b* (yellowness)	55.60 ± 0.88

The average yolk height, yolk width and yolk weight were 21.35±0.23 mm, 50.79±0.53 mm and 35.02±0.98 g respectively. The L (brightness), a (redness) and b (yellowness) yolk color traits were 55.67±0.46, 13.06±0.37 and 55.60±0.88 respectively. The yolk index and yolk percentage were 42.07±0.49% and 38.85±0.96% respectively. In line with findings of this study, similar results in terms of yolk weight, yolk height, yolk width and yolk index have been reported in Pekin ducks [14, 16, 18].

Table 3. The albumen traits of French Pekin ducks evaluated

Albumen weight (g)	42.01 ± 0.88
Albumen height (mm)	8.16±0.23
Albumen width (mm)	67.91±1.21
Albumen length (mm)	106.26±1.63
Albumen index (%)	42.07±0.49
Albumen percentage (%)	46.67±1.02
Albumen pH	9.30±0.11
Yolk to albumen ratio (%)	84.03±3.14
Haugh unit (%)	82.43±1.51

The albumen height, albumen width and albumen length were 8.16±0.23 mm, 67.91±1.21 mm and 106.26±1.63 mm respectively. The albumen pH, albumen weight and albumen index were 9.30±0.11, 42.01±0.88g and 9.39±0.30% respectively. The albumen percentage and yolk to albumen ratio were 46.67±1.02% and 84.03±3.14% respectively. The Haugh unit was 82.43±1.51. In line with the reports of the present study, some authors [18, 17, 15, 14] have reported similar albumen weight, albumen height, albumen length, albumen pH and albumen index values in Pekin ducks.

Conclusion

The increase in the production of Pekin ducks as an alternative poultry specie in addition to the production of chicken for meat and eggs could serve as a means of meeting the rise in demand for poultry meat and eggs especially, in developing and underdeveloped countries. Pekin ducks as an alternative poultry has low maintenance and production cost with their eggs being highly nutritional and healthy, making them one of the best alternative poultry species for commercial egg production. Egg quality traits are important economic parameters that influenced the consumer's purchasing power, production cost and the total economic profit of farmers and in this study, it was concluded that the internal and the external egg quality traits of the French Pekin ducks studied were within the normal range.

References

- [1] Jalaludeen A, Churchil RR. Duck eggs and their nutritive value. Centre for Advanced Studies in Poultry Science College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences Mannuthy, Thrissur, Kerala. Poultry Line. 2006.
- [2] Al-Obaidi FA, Al-Shadeedi SMJ. Comparison study of egg morphology, component and chemical composition of Mallard duck and domestic Peking duck. *Journal of Biological Innovations*. 2016). 5(4), 555-562.
- [3] Ahmad I, Alam MJ, Sajedul Haque M, Mamdud, MAA. Proximate analysis and assessment the physical characteristics of different types of duck eggs in Bangladesh. *Journal of Engineering and Science Research*. 2017. 1(2), 38-42.
- [4] Quan TH, Benjakul S. Duck egg albumen: physicochemical and functional properties as affected by storage and processing. *Journal of food science and technology*. 2019. 56, 1104-1115.
- [5] Pingel H. Waterfowl production for food security. *Proceed. in IV World Waterfowl Conference*, Thrissur, India. 2009.
- [6] Yang N. Social economic aspects of egg production in China. 2011. 17-26.
- [7] FAO. Guides Duck Breeders in Increasing Production. 2018. www.fao.org/indonesia/news/detail-events/en/c/1099183.
- [8] Aendo P, Netvichian R, Tippayalak S, Sanguankiat A, Khuntamoon T, Songserm T, Tulayakul P.. Health risk contamination of heavy metals in yolk and albumen of duck eggs collected in central and western Thailand. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2018. 184:501–507
- [9] Dunn IC, Joseph NT, Bain M, Edmond A, Wilson PW, Milona P, Nys Y, Gautron J, Schmutz M, Preisinger R, Waddington D. *Animal Genetics*. 2009. 40: (1) 110-4
- [10] Roland DA. The extent of uncollected eggs due to inadequate shell. *Poultry Sci*. 1977. 56:1517-1521.

- [11] Carnarius KM, Conrad KM, Mast MG, Macneil JH. Relationship of eggshell ultrastructure and shell strength to the soundness of shell eggs. *Poultry Science*. 1996. 75(5), 656-663.
- [12] Madison ME, Perez AM. U.S. Egg and Poultry Statistical Series, 1960-1992. United States Department of Agriculture. Statistical Bulletin Number 872. USDA, Washington, DC. 1994.
- [13] Kuru B, Kirmizibayrak T, Cengiz M, Işık S. The effect of egg weight on egg external quality characteristics and hatching performance in Pekin ducks. *Kafkas Üniversitesi Veteriner Fakültesi Dergisi*. 2023. 29(4).
- [14] Biesiada-Drzazga B, Charuta A, Banaszewska D. Evaluation of particular traits of Pekin duck breed STAR 53 of French origin eggs during egg laying. *Veterinarija ir zootechnika*. 2014. 67(89).
- [15] Yuan J, Wang B, Huang Z, Fan Y, Huang C, Hou Z. Comparisons of egg quality traits, egg weight loss and hatchability between striped and normal duck eggs. *British poultry science*. 2013. 54(2), 265-269.
- [16] Harikrishnan S, Ponnuvel P. A glance at internal and external qualities of Kuttanad, White Pekin and commercial duck eggs. *Indian Journal of Veterinary Sciences & Biotechnology*. 2012. 7(4), 38-40.
- [17] Lu L, Xue Y, Asiamah CA, Zou K, Liu Y, Su Y. Evaluation of egg-laying performance, egg quality traits, and nutritional values of eggs of Leizhou Black Duck. *European Poultry Science/Archiv für Geflügelkunde*. 2020. (319).
- [18] Ipek A, Sozcu A. Comparison of hatching egg characteristics, embryo development, yolk absorption, hatch window, and hatchability of Pekin Duck eggs of different weights. *Poultry Science*. 2017. 96(10), 3593-3599.